

Fast and accurate differential transcript usage by testing equivalence class counts

Supplementary Material

Marek Cmero¹, Nadia Davidson^{1,2*}, Alicia Oshlack^{1,2*}

1. Murdoch Children's Research Institute, Flemington Road, Parkville, Australia
2. School of Biosciences, Faculty of Science, University of Melbourne, Melbourne, Victoria, Australia

*These authors contributed equally in supervision of this work

List of Figures

1	Dispersion vs. normalised counts	2
2	Significant gene overlap from Bottomly data	3
3	Subset testing results	4
4	Rank-order plot	5
5	Kallisto vs. Salmon on Bottomly tests	5
6	Results with and without filtering	6
7	Example EC usage plot	6
8	Performance on Love data	7

List of Tables

1	RAM usage	8
2	Features per gene	8

Supplementary Figure 1: Shows the dispersion versus mean normalised counts for all features across the three data sets, generated using DEXSeq's 'plotDispEsts' function. As described in Love et al. [1], the red line shows the fitted dispersion-mean trend, the blue dots indicate the shrunken dispersion estimates, and the blue circles indicate outliers not shrunken towards the prior.

Supplementary Figure 2: Shows the significant genes ($FDR < 0.05$) shared between the methods, obtained from DEXSeq run on the full Bottomly et al. [2] data set for each feature.

Supplementary Figure 3: Shows the ability of the three methods to recreate the results of a full comparison (10 vs. 11) of the Bottomly et al. [2] data using random subsets of 3 vs. 3 samples across 20 iterations using $FDR < 0.05$ ($FDR = 0.05$ is indicated by the dotted line). The lines between the plots join data points from the same iteration. Each row uses a different 'truth' set: union is the set of genes called significant by any method, intersect is the set of genes called significant by all methods, and individual is the set of genes called significant by that method only.

Supplementary Figure 4: The number of false positives versus each gene's rank (by FDR) for one iteration (3 vs. 3) of the Bottomly [2] subset tests for the top 500 genes. The union of significant genes across all methods was used as the truth set.

Supplementary Figure 5: Kallisto [3] versus Salmon's [4] performance on the Bottomly [2] subset testing experiments, using each method's significant genes from the full (10 vs. 11) run as the truth set for calculating both metrics.

Supplementary Figure 6: Performance of ECC, transcript count (using Salmon) and exon count (using DEXSeq-count) methods on the Soneson [5] data with and without *DRIMSeq* [6] filtering (see paper methods for full filtering criteria).

Supplementary Figure 7: An example EC usage plot for a single gene from the Soneson [5] *hsapiens* DECU results. Log EC usage is shown across each equivalence class for both conditions. Yellow blocks indicate significant ECs. As ECs do not correspond easily to genomic locations, no special ordering is applied the ECs. In the given example, transcripts mapping to each significant EC can be obtained. The significant ec142580 corresponds to a single transcript (ENST00000443443), indicating that interpretation can be straight-forward if the EC is associated with a single transcript. See Section 6.4 of the EC DTU vignette for how to run the plotting code.

Supplementary Figure 8: Performance of ECC, transcript count (using Salmon) and exon count (using DEXSeq-count) methods on the Love et al. [7] data (12 vs. 12 samples). The points show nominal FDR cutoffs of 0.01, 0.05 and 0.1.

Supplementary Table 1: Maximum RAM usage for each job in GB (total by process). Each task was run as specified in the compute times table in the main paper (Table 1). (ds = DEXSeq’s counting method; fc = featureCounts.)

drosophila	Transcripts	ECs	Exons (ds)	Exons (fc)
Alignment	-	-	6.61	6.61
Quantification	1.72	1.5	0.5	0.24
Match ECs	-	0.52	-	-
DEXSeq DTU	1.25	1.89	1.52	1.39
Max	1.72	1.89	1.52	1.39

hsapiens	Transcripts	ECs	Exons (ds)	Exons (fc)
Alignment	-	-	33.24	33.24
Quantification	3.8	3.58	1.14	0.29
Match ECs	-	3.82	-	-
DEXSeq DTU	3.12	4.85	4.85	5.78
Max	3.8	4.85	33.24	33.24

mouse (Bottomly)	Transcripts	ECs	Exons (ds)	Exons (fc)
Alignment	-	-	25.13	25.13
Quantification	2.59	2.42	0.59	0.27
Match ECs	-	3.17	-	-
DEXSeq DTU	3.2	8.53	6.58	0.59
Max	3.2	8.53	25.13	25.13

Supplementary Table 2: Average number of exons and transcripts per gene from the hg38 ensembl reference.

Features	Mean count
Exons	11.8885
Transcripts	3.5045

References

- [1] Michael I. Love, Wolfgang Huber, and Simon Anders. Moderated estimation of fold change and dispersion for RNA-seq data with DESeq2. *Genome Biology*, 15(12):1–21, 2014.
- [2] Daniel Bottomly, Nicole A.R. Walter, Jessica Ezzell Hunter, Priscila Darakjian, Sunita Kawane, Kari J. Buck, Robert P. Searles, Michael Mooney, Shannon K. McWeeney, and Robert Hitzemann. Evaluating gene expression in C57BL/6J and DBA/2J mouse striatum using RNA-Seq and microarrays. *PLoS ONE*, 6(3), 2011.
- [3] Nicolas L. Bray, Harold Pimentel, Páll Melsted, and Lior Pachter. Near-optimal probabilistic RNA-seq quantification. *Nature Biotechnology*, 34(5):525–527, 2016.

- [4] Rob Patro, Geet Duggal, Michael I Love, Rafael A Irizarry, and Carl Kingsford. Salmon provides fast and bias-aware quantification of transcript expression. *Nature Methods*, 14(4):021592, 2017.
- [5] Charlotte Soneson, Katarina L. Matthes, Malgorzata Nowicka, Charity W. Law, and Mark D. Robinson. Isoform prefiltering improves performance of count-based methods for analysis of differential transcript usage. *Genome Biology*, 17(1):1–15, 2016.
- [6] Malgorzata Nowicka and Mark D. Robinson. DRIMSeq: a Dirichlet-multinomial framework for multivariate count outcomes in genomics. *F1000Research*, 5(0):1356, 2016.
- [7] Michael I. Love, Charlotte Soneson, and Rob Patro. *Swimming downstream: statistical analysis of differential transcript usage following Salmon quantification*, volume 7. 2018.